

CEDEFOP

European Centre for the Development
of Vocational Training

50
YEARS
SHAPING LEARNING AND
SKILLS FOR EUROPE

Cedefop's European Vocational Teacher survey (EVTS)

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VET4youth-teachers and trainers team facilitator

EUROPEAN SECTORAL SOCIAL DIALOGUE IN EDUCATION

Plenary meeting

2 December 2025

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25 SEP 2025

PRESS RELEASE

CEDEFOP

Cedefop launches the first European Vocational Teacher Survey to tackle critical VET teacher shortages

26 SEP 2025

NEWS

HEADLINES

VET teachers take the stage: Cedefop launches the first European survey to secure Europe's skilled future

Europe's first survey for VET teachers: Listening, learning, acting

Poland		
Portugal		
Romania		
Slovenia		
Slovakia		
Finland		
Sweden		
Croatia		

All teachers in initial VET schools at ISCED level 3

22 EU Member States on board

Random two-stage sampling (VET schools-teachers)

More than 10 000 interviews in total (differentiated by country)

A. ELIGIBILITY

Teacher at ISCED 3
VET institution

B. PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE

Teaching and non-teaching experience, teaching field(s), permanent post, multiple jobs

G. PERSONAL DRIVERS

Education, field and teaching qualification, learning motivation and orientation, self-efficacy, professional values

D. CPD NEEDS

Vocational excellence, inclusive VET, sustainability, digital/AI

C. CPD ACTIVITIES

Type (courses, seminars, conferences, study visits)
Online or offline
Organised by

- school
- industry
- own (learning by doing, observation, reflection, trial and error, peer-learning, feedback)

VET-workplace boundaries
Mandatory / consequences
Duration
Quality
School support
Barriers

F. SCHOOL ENVIRONMENT

Size, school ownership, transformational and participative leadership, innovative school climate, organisational commitment

E. WORK ORGANISATION

Task and goal interdependence, autonomy, digital resources

E. WORKING CONDITIONS

Working hours, workload, teacher shortages, stress-burnout-ill health, job satisfaction, earnings, material deprivation

D. PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT

Improvement in what/how to teach, use of resources, inclusion, collaboration

EUROPEAN VET TEACHER SURVEY

Pilot findings

735 VET teachers from 23 EU MS
Non-representative sample-Please treat with caution

Pilot findings confirm **low social status of VET teachers**

13%

Receive an adequate salary for the work done

9%

VET teachers are valued in their country

Working conditions: Heavy workload due to teacher shortages

49%

Took on additional tasks
cause of teaching shortage
at school

37%

have too many
administrative
tasks

31%

say they have
too much
work

Working Conditions: Other stress factors

20%

have too many students

27%

constantly maintain
discipline among their
students

Impact on well-being

42% ANXIETY

16% DEPRESSION

**17% SHORTNESS
OF BREATH**

**33,5% INCREASED
BLOOD PRESSURE**

**40% HEART
POUNING OR
RACING**

**28% STOMACH
CRUMBS OR PAIN**

**60% PHYSICAL
EXHAUSTION**

**60% SLEEPING
DIFFICULTIES**

Job satisfaction

~ 1 in 3

feel they are not progressing in their job as fast as they would like

35%

feel intellectually stimulated in their job

Limited support for their professional development

35%

never released from teaching duties to participate in CPD

59%

never granted days off or study leave for training

33%

never had their training expenses covered by school

Only 1 in 2 teachers are sufficiently supported by their school to participate in CPD

Readiness for inclusive VET

Teachers need to further develop their skills in

Teachers use digital technologies to a large extent

Teachers' needs for further development in digital skills

33%

in using digital technologies for **teaching**

31%

in making learning more **accessible** for vulnerable students

29%

in using digital tech. for student **assessment**

32%

in assessing the **potential risks** of using digital technologies in teaching

Limited use of advanced digital technologies such as AI

use AI technologies **very often** as part of their work

31%

need to further develop in identifying **which AI technologies are relevant** for their work

35%

need to further develop in **assessing the potential risks, biases & ethical issues** for the use of AI

43%

Do not believe that a robot or an intelligent machine will replace them in the next 10 years ...

Who feel less professionally developed? (regression analysis-baseline model)

Lack of VET teacher professional development

Spread the word to support our campaign

The European Vocational Teacher Survey 2025-2026

Teacher shortage - what needs to change?

EVTS EUROPEAN VOCATIONAL TEACHER SURVEY

The European Vocational Teacher Survey 2025-2026

Wellbeing in schools - How can we support it?

EVTS EUROPEAN VOCATIONAL TEACHER SURVEY

The European Vocational Teacher Survey 2025-2026

Career development for teachers - how can we do better?

EVTS EUROPEAN VOCATIONAL TEACHER SURVEY

The European Vocational Teacher Survey 2025-2026

Resources for teachers and students - where do we fall short?

EVTS EUROPEAN VOCATIONAL TEACHER SURVEY

Thank you

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